

INFLUENCE OF COMPACTION BEHAVIOR OF CARBON NCF ON PREFORM MECHANICS FOR CONTINUOUS PROFILE PREFORMING

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ABSTRACT

Preforming is one of the main process steps of the manufacturing chain of Liquid Composite Molding processes which is mostly driven by extensive manual effort. However, by increasing the automation of the preforming process and the usage of process-related material configurations it is possible to increase the preforming efficiency and enable mass production.

During processing with the newly developed fully automated Continuous Profile Preforming System (CPPS), it was recognized that the continuous forming behavior of non-crimped fabrics (NCF) is dependent on the utilized preform configuration. Thereby, the initially flat textiles get stressed by compaction, friction, and bending. Hence, the overall target is to identify the main influencing factors to improve the continuous forming process.

In doing so, the compaction behavior of dry single-ply and multi-ply fabric stacks (preforms) was examined. Based on current continuous preforming conditions, the investigated range of fiber volume content is limited between 40 – 50 %. Utilizing five carbon fiber NCF, differing in type of stitching (tricot, pillar, and hybrid) and superficial density (300 g/m² and 600 g/m²), the influence of material parameters (number of layers and stacking sequence) as well as process parameters (testing velocity and pre-compaction cycles) was investigated. The results showed, that 6-ply preforms (superficial weight 300 g/m²) require up to 88 % higher compaction forces than 3-ply preforms (superficial weight 600 g/m²) even though the total superficial density remained equal. Furthermore, pre-compaction cycles (up to 8) reduce the required compaction forces of preforms up to 69 %, whereby the initial cycle has the most effect. Also the stacking sequence of 6-ply preforms strongly influences the compaction force. In this context the main influencing factors were the stitching seam pattern and their alignment to each other.

1 INTRODUCTION

By using fiber reinforced polymer composites (FRPC) it is possible to guarantee a high degree of design flexibility and weight reduction of components. Correspondingly, in the aerospace, automotive, wind energy, and shipping industry FRPC have been widely used within the last years. In near future, the growth of demand for FRPCs will constantly increase and new application possibilities will arise [1].

Nowadays, high manufacturing costs often limit a broad application, which is contributed to the lack of automation of the processes as well as the unused potential of process-related material selection. The meaning of process-related material selection is that the materials should be selected and stacked due to their forming properties (bending, friction, shearing, and compaction) to e.g. decrease the external loads on the materials during processing.

Liquid composite molding (LCM) processes are promising manufacturing processes to realize both small to mass productions of high-quality FRPC components. One of the most used process variants is Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) [2]. By the usage of robotic arms with adaptive handling systems or continuous preforming systems the extensive manual preforming effort (cutting, orientating, stacking, draping, etc.) can be decreased [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]. Thus, it is currently not enough to enable mass production. Two possible ways exist to extent the limitation: increasing the degree of automation or

utilizing process-related material configurations.

Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH developed a Continuous Profile Preforming System (CPPS) to increase the automation of the preforming process. Starting with the material from the roll, the CPPS enables the fully automated manufacturing of T- or I-profile preforms. Currently, 4 m/min can be achieved by using stitching and not binder as fixation technology. Thus, during processing it could be observed that manufacturing speed and the quality of the profile preforms strongly depends on the utilized material or rather preform configuration. To consider these dependencies, it is necessary to understand the forming process.

During the continuous forming process of the CPPS, the processed fabrics get simultaneously stressed by bending, friction, and compaction (see Figure 1) [6].

Figure 1: Influencing factors on the continuous forming process of the CPPS: Friction, bending, and compaction behavior of the textiles as well as process conditions.

Concerning bending and friction, past studies have shown that the forming process can be improved by process-related material selections [6, 11]. But also the compaction behavior influences the required loads to reach a target fiber-volume-content at the end of the forming unit. Furthermore, it is a dominating factor to keep the fiber-volume-content during the guidance through the system. Consequently, it is important to investigate the influence of material and process parameters on compaction behavior as well.

In the past, a lot of work referring to compaction of technical textiles for FRPC applications was performed. Basic compaction effects of NCFs, weaves, and mats were identified by varying process and materials parameters. Several scientists defined yarn bending, yarn flattening, yarn cross-section deformation, void / gap condensation, and nesting as the basic compaction effects [12, 13, 14]. Depending on the material itself and the current period of testing different effects are dominant [12, 13, 14, 15, 16]. Comparing weaves with NCFs for example, yarn flattening and yarn bending are more dominant when a perpendicular load gets applied. Additionally, weaves have an increased ability to slide into each other (nesting effect) when testing multi-ply samples, which decrease the compaction force to reach a targeted fiber-volume-content [12, 14, 17, 18, 19]. Other studies showed almost no effect with increasing ply number and the resulting compaction force remained almost constant [20, 21].

When testing multi-ply stacks of one or different fabrics various statements have been made with varying stacking sequences (alternating, half / half or mixed). Depending on the type of fabric, the resistance against compaction was decreased [20], increased [16], or remains constant [21]. The findings of the past have shown, that compaction behavior of NCFs differs to weaves or mats due to its nature of aligned fibers [22] and the presence of stitching seams.

Also the process parameters (testing speed and multiple compaction cycles) influence the compaction behavior of textile fiber structures. By increasing the compaction speed the resistance against compaction loads is increasing as well due to the dependence to the viscoelastic response of

textiles. [16, 22, 23]

Furthermore, multiple compaction cycles decrease the required compaction force to reach the targeted fiber-volume-content. With a higher number of repetitions the required compaction force is lower or a higher fiber-volume-content can be reached while keeping the maximum compaction force constant [16, 17, 24, 25]. The highest number of repetitions (51 cycles) was applied by Robitaille and Gauvin [25], whereby the individually reached fiber-volume-contents were steadily increasing. Consequently, also plastic deformation takes place when testing textile preforms.

The findings of the past showed, that the influence of material and process parameters on compaction are partly various and material-dependent and cannot be directly transferred to continuous preforming processes. Therefore, the influence of several material and process parameters on compaction behavior of five selected carbon NCFs was investigated in the following paragraphs. Then, different possibilities were evaluated to improve the continuous preforming process based on the previously gained results.

2 RESEARCH APPROACH

This study investigates the influence of compaction behavior of five carbon non-crimped fabrics (NCF) between a fiber-volume-content of 40 – 50 %. The target fiber-volume-content range is based on current preforming conditions. The utilized materials differ in their fiber orientation (two NCFs are 0°/90°, two ±45°, and one 0°±45°), in their individual superficial density (300 g/m², 600 g/m²), and type of stitching (tricot, chain, hybrid). Table 1 summarizes the applied process and material parameters which were examined to investigate the compaction behavior of dry single-ply and multi-ply fabric stacks.

Process and material parameters	Test parameters and units
Ply number	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 15 plies
Stacking sequence	Consecutively stacked, alternating, half/half; Individual plies turned upside down within one stack; Every 2nd ply turned 45° (offset) within one stack
Compaction speed	1, 50, 100 [mm/min]
Number of repetitive compaction cycles	1 - 10 [cycles]
Pre-compaction cycles	1, 2, 4, 8 [cycles]

Table 1: Overview of investigated process and material parameters including test parameters and units

Based on the results, potential process and process-related material (preform) modifications will be evaluated to improve the continuous preforming process.

3 MATERIALS

The compaction tests were performed on five carbon fiber NCFs from SGL Group. The specifications of the textiles are listed in Table 2. The textiles were split into two groups: Group I (M1 and M2) has a superficial density of 300 g/m² and group II (M3 – M5) has a superficial density of 600 g/m².

Group / mark	SGL Group	Superficial density [g/m ²]	Total superficial density [g/m ²]	Type of stitching	Gauge ["]	Stitching length [mm]	Fiber orientation [°]	Uncompacted thickness [mm]	
Group I	M1	HPT 300 C090	145	297	Trikot	6	3.33	0/90	0.3
	M2	HPT 300 C45	145	296	Pillar	6	2.6	±45	0.3
Group II	M3	HPT 610 C090	300	607	Trikot	7	2.7	0/90	0.6
	M4	HPT 610 C45	300	606	Pillar	6	2.5	±45	0.6
	M5	HPT 610 C045	200	608	Hybrid	6	2.5	0/±45	0.6

Table 2: Overview of the five investigated carbon fiber NCFs

4 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A universal testing machine ZWICK 1474 was utilized to investigate the compaction behavior of M1 – M5. Before testing, the materials were cut (diameter of 100 mm), stacked (1 - 15 plies), and weighed. Then, they were placed in between the two metal measuring plates (supported by a ball joint) which were mounted on the ZWICK 1474 (see Figure 2). The testing procedure started with the lateral movement of the lower plate. The set testing velocity (1, 50 or 100 mm/min) was kept constant until the maximum load (20 kN) was reached. After a holding time of 2 min at 20 kN, the load was released and the tested sample could be removed. Concerning the multiple compaction cycles, the previous testing procedure was repeated on the same sample until 10 cycles were performed.

Figure 2: Test set-up to measure the compaction behavior of a textile sample utilizing a ZWICK 1474

The analyzing software testXpert II was used to record time, force, and vertical movement of the lower measuring plate. Utilizing the ply number n , the fiber density ρ , the superficial weight of the textile g , and the distance between the plates h_p , it is possible to calculate the current fiber-volume-content v_f :

$$v_f = \frac{n * g}{\rho * h_p} \quad (1)$$

The tests were performed by a humidity of 65 ± 5 % and ambient temperature 22.5 ± 2 °C. Also blind curves were performed (testing without samples between the plates) and subtracted from the forces of the compaction tests to compensate inherent measurement errors of the load cell. Each measurement configuration was repeated three to five times for statistical coverage and the analysis was performed with MS Excel.

5 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

5.1 Influence of material parameters on compaction

Only qualitative trends can be indicated by the performed single-ply tests. This is contributed to the material inhomogeneity of the fiber structure and the cutting process in terms of the sample preparation. Especially for the lighter materials of group I (M1 and M2) high standard deviations were measured (see Figure 3). The force progressions of the single-ply tested samples M1 – M5 are displayed by a polynomial of fifth order (method of least squares) between a fiber-volume-content of 40 – 50 %.

Figure 3: Force progression of the single-ply tested carbon NCFs M1 – M5

The results indicate that the textiles of group II are easier to compress than the group I textiles. Comparing M1 respectively M2 (biaxial NCFs) with M3 respectively M4 (cf. Table 2) only the superficial weight is different and twice as many yarns are bundled regarding M3 or M4. Consequently, the cross-sections of the CF-yarns are thicker and more circular. When a perpendicular load gets applied to reach a target fiber-volume-content, the thicker bundles of M3 and M4 can be compressed more easily due to cross-section deformations of the CF yarns. Also the triaxial NCF M5 of group II is easier to compress than group I materials.

The investigation of multi-ply stacks will help to substantiate the previous observations. Furthermore, the influence of the number of plies can be detected. The results showed that the influence of increasing number of plies for M1 - M5 can be neglected between a fiber-volume-content of 40 – 50 %, which is in compliance with the findings of Hammami and Gebart [20] and Liu et al. [21]. For e.g. M2 the average compaction force amounts to 109 N (fvc = 45 %) respectively 353 N (fvc = 45 %), whereby only 12 N respectively 48 N are required for M5. The same coherences were measured for the other fabrics (M1, M3 and M4), which confirms the previous trends. Only at higher

compaction levels (fvc = 50 %) an influence of the number of plies could be observed, but the high standard deviations do not allow to make a clear statement.

Due to the results of single-ply and multi-ply compactions tests it is reasonable to proof if a benefit can be achieved for continuous preforming. As previously mentioned, the forming behavior depends on several material characteristics like friction, bending, shearing, and compaction. By decreasing one of these factors, like the compaction resistance for instance, it is possible to decrease the external loads on the preforms and process improvements can be achieved. Therefore, 6-ply stacks of group I materials were compared with 3-ply stacks of group II materials (Figure 4). The number of plies for each configuration correlates to an industrial profile thickness of 3.5 mm at a fiber-volume-content of 58 %.

Figure 4: Influence of single superficial weight on compaction force of preforms at 40 % and 50 % fiber volume content (fvc); 6 plies (6p) of group I (M1, M2) vs. 3 plies (3p) of group II (M3, M4, M5)

The preforms consisting of group II materials (3-ply stacks) can be compressed up to 88 % easier than the group I preforms (6-ply stacks), although the total superficial weight was the same. This difference is caused by the much higher amount (twice as much) of stitching yarns of the 6-ply stacks (group I preforms) and the increased resistance against compaction of the group I materials. The same percentage differences were measured for 2-ply stacks (group I) compared to 1-ply stacks (group II) as well as for 4-ply stacks (group I) compared to 2-ply stacks (group II).

5.2 Influence of process parameters on compaction

To investigate the influence of testing velocity a 6-ply stack of M1 (group I) was compressed at 1, 50, and 100 mm/min (see Figure 5). It can be clearly seen that with increasing compaction velocity the resistance against compaction is increased as well. This is contributed to the viscoelastic behavior of textile materials [16, 22, 23]. The same effect was measurable for the group II materials, but at much lower compaction levels.

Figure 5: Influence of testing velocity (1, 50, and 100 mm/min) utilizing a 6-ply stack of M1

Concerning multiple compaction cycles different 3-ply stacks (group II) and 6-ply stacks (group I) were tested. Figure 6 exemplary shows the progression of the compaction force (45 % and 50 % fvc) of a 3-ply stacked preform of M3 up to a cycle number of 10 repetitive cycles. The relaxation time between each cycle was 1 min.

Figure 6: Influence of multiple compaction cycles (1 – 10) on compaction behavior of a 3-ply stacked Preform M3; Compaction curves for 45 % and 50 % fvc are displayed

Compared to the first compaction cycle the amount of 10 multiple compaction cycles reduces the compaction force between 86 - 94 % (depending on the fiber-volume-content). However, the highest reductions were observed between the first and the second cycle. For example, 67 % respectively 61 % less force needs to be applied to reach a fvc of 45 % or 50 %. But with increasing number of repetitive cycles (up to 10), the compaction curves flatten out and only 2 - 17 % less force is required to reach the desired fiber-volume-content between the last two cycles (nine to ten).

Identical results were measured for the 6-ply stacks of group II materials. After 10 repetitive compaction cycles a total reduction up to 87 % could be achieved, whereby the first compaction cycle reduced the compaction force to 56 % respectively 61 % for a fiber-volume-content of 40 % or 50 %.

For all tests, no stagnation could be achieved up to ten repetitive cycles. Robitaille and Gauvin [25] have applied up to 51 repetitions and observed similar curve progressions.

To transfer the findings of the multiple test series a pre-compaction unit was built to simulate a pre-compaction unit, which could be integrated in front of the forming unit of the CPPS. The test set-up consists of two vertically movable aluminum rollers (orientated parallel to each other) to perform pre-compaction cycles utilizing the same sample size ($\varnothing = 100$ mm) as for the compaction tests (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Test set-up for pre-compaction cycles

The gap between two movable rollers corresponds to the cavity height of the universal testing machine. Before testing, the gap was set referring to the utilized type of material stack. For e.g. M1 (6-ply), the gap was set to 1.7 mm (fvc ~ 55 %). Then, the textile samples were passed 1, 2, 4 or 8 times through the gap before they were transferred to the universal testing machine. The comparison of compaction force (6-ply stack of M1) between repetitive compaction cycles and a single compaction cycle after n_i ($i = 1, 2, 4, 8$) pre-compaction cycles at a fiber-volume-content of 45 % is displayed in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Comparison of compaction force between repetitive compaction cycles and a single cycle including n_i ($i = 1, 2, 4, 8$) pre-compaction cycles of a 6-ply stack M1; fiber-volume-content is 45 %.

By applying pre-compaction cycles, a very low level of compaction forces could be achieved even after the first pre-compaction cycle. The necessary compaction force to reach a fiber-volume-content of 45 % could be reduced by one pre-compaction about 45 % compared to the compaction cycles

without pre-compaction. Furthermore, two pre-compaction cycles have an additional reducing effect and the resultant compaction force was 62 % less. Additional pre-compaction cycles (up to 8) did not have a pronounced extra effect and the force leveled out around 150 N for M1.

In conclusion it can be said, that pre-compaction of fabrics enormously reduce the compaction force (major reduction after the first cycle). The effect can be increased with increasing the pre-compaction condition due to e.g. decreasing the gap distance between the rollers.

5.3 Influence of stacking sequence on compaction

By changing the stacking sequence within one stack the compaction behavior can be positively influenced as well. Several strategies exist: stacking one material with an offset (e.g. every second ply is rotated 45°), mixing different types of fabrics, or turning individual plies upside down.

The NCF fabrics of this study have shown a reduction of compaction resistance which can be achieved if the preforms are stacked with an offset every second ply. The highest reduction could be observed by group I materials. For M1, the compaction force could be decreased between 12 - 38 % to achieve a fiber-volume-content of 40 - 50 % compared to consecutively stacked preforms. Concerning M2, a reduction of 5 - 16 % was reachable. This effect is contributed to the superposition of stitching seams which gets changed by introducing an offset. In contrast to consecutively stacked preforms, the stitching seams are spread more even along the sample surface and the number of superimposed seams is decreased. Hammami and Gebart [20] have observed the same results for stitched UD fabrics.

By turning individual plies upside down within the stack, Equally Orientated Textile Interfaces (EOTI) can be built which enable nesting. As mentioned before, the nesting effect reduces the compaction resistance to reach a target fiber-volume-content and appears more often for weaves [12, 14, 17, 18]. But within the EOTIs the CF-yarns are equally orientated which enable nesting (see Figure 9).

Figure 9: Schematic compaction behavior of two plies of M1 (uncompacted ↔ compacted) when an EOTI exists or not

Three different stacking sequences of 6-ply stacks of M1 were tested: Case A represents the reference with no EOTI, case B exhibits three EOTI (four plies are upside down), and case C exhibits five EOTI (three plies are upside down). Figure 10 displays the three different preforms. Furthermore, two different 3-ply stacks of M3 were tested as well and compared with the M1 configurations: Case D represents the reference and Case E exhibits two EOTI (middle ply is turned upside down). Figure 11 displays the resultant force progressions of the different cases A - E.

It can be clearly seen that the compaction force could be reduced by turning individual plies upside down (case A ↔ case B and C). A reduction of 6 - 33 % respectively 8 - 42 % results when testing case B (6-ply stack of M1 containing 3 EOTI) respectively case C (6-ply stack of M1 containing 5 EOTI) compared to the reference (case A). Concerning M3, the EOTIs do not have a pronounced reducing effect (< 9 %). Thus, by using a 3-ply stack of M3 instead of a 6-ply stack of M1 a higher reduction is present (cf. Figure 4).

Figure 10: Schematically set-up of three 6-ply stacks of M1 (0°/90° oriented NCF). Case A: reference with no EOTI; Case B: three EOTI (four plies are upside down); Case C: five EOTI (three plies are upside down)

Figure 11: Influence of EOTI on compaction behavior of 6-ply and 3-ply stacked preforms utilizing M1 and M3: Case A = M1 reference, case B = M1 with 3 EOTI, case C = M1 with 5 EOTI, case D = M3 reference, and case E = M3 with 2 EOTI

In conclusion, it can be stated that a pronounced reduction can be achieved by changing the stacking sequence within one stack (especially for group I materials). Nesting takes place when equally, and the more EOTI exist within one stack the less compaction force is required to achieve a targeted fvc. But a higher reduction can be achieved by using less heavy plies (3-ply stacks of group II) instead of more light plies (6-ply stacks of group I) containing EOTIs while keeping the total weight of the preforms equal.

6 CONCLUSION

The influence of several process (testing velocity and multiple compaction cycles) and material parameters (number of layers and stacking sequence) on compaction behavior of dry single-ply and multi-ply fabric stacks was investigated.

The findings of this study are listed below:

- Textiles with higher superficial weight are easier to compact and more suitable to achieve robust processes.
- Higher testing speeds result in increased compaction resistance.
- Multiple compaction cycles lead to decreasing compaction resistance of textiles.
- The alignment (superposition) of stitching seams remarkably influences the compaction behavior of NCF preforms.
- Nesting can be achieved by turning individual plies upside down due to equally orientated textile interfaces (EOTI). In addition, the more EOTI exist within one stack the less compaction force is required to achieve a targeted fvc.

Two possibilities were found to potentially improve the continuous forming process of the CPPS. Concerning the process, a pre-compaction unit will be integrated in front of the forming unit of the CPPS and evaluated. Furthermore, promising process-related material (preform) configurations including several equally orientated textile interfaces (EOTIs) will be processed.

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REFERENCES

- [1] VDI Zentrum Ressourceneffizienz GmbH (VDI ZRE), *Kurzanalyse Nr. 3 und Dokumentation des Fachgesprächs. Kohlenstofffaserverstärkte Kunststoffe im Fahrzeugbau – Ressourceneffizienz und Technologien*, 2013.
- [2] M. Neitzel, P. Mitschang, U. Breuer, *Handbuch Verbundwerkstoffe - Werkstoffe, Verarbeitung, Anwendung*, 2. Auflage, München, Deutschland, 2014.
- [3] G. Reinhart and G. Straßer, Flexible gripping technology for the automated handling of limp technical textiles in composites industry, *Production Engineering*, **5**, 2011, pp. 301-306.
- [4] G. Seliger, F. Szimmat, J. Niemeier, and J. Stephan, Automated Handling of Non-Rigid Parts, *Annals of the CIRP*, **52**, 1, 2003, pp. 21-24.
- [5] M. Wiedemann and M. Sinapius, *Adaptive, Tolerant and Efficient Composites Structures - Research Topics in Aerospace*, 2013, pp. 317-324.
- [6] T. Grieser and P. Mitschang, Production of continuously formed high performance preforms for FRPC profiles, *Conference proceedings ECCM15, Venice, 2012*.
- [7] H. Purol, *Entwicklung kontinuierlicher Preformingverfahren zur Herstellung gekrümmter CFK-Versteifungsprofile*, Dissertation Universität Bremen, 2011.
- [8] P. Mitschang, A. Ogale, J. Schlimbach, F. Weyrauch and C. Weimer, Preform technology: A necessary requirement for quality controlled LCM-processes, *Polymers & Polymer Composites*, **11**, 8, 2003, pp. 605-622.
- [9] C. Weimer and P. Mitschang, Aspects of the stitch formation process on the quality of sewn multi-textile-preforms, *Composites Part A – Applied Science and Technology*, **32**, 10, 2001, pp. 1477-1484.

- [10] C. Weimer, T. Preller, P. Mitschang and K. Drechsler, Approach to net-shape preforming using textile technologies. Part I: edges. *Composites Part A – Applied Science and Technology*, **31**, 11, 2000, pp. 1261-1268.
- [11] T. Grieser and P. Mitschang, Kontinuierliches Profil-Preforming für Verstärkungsstrukturen, *Lightweight Design*, **4**, 2014, pp. 24-29.
- [12] B. Chen, E. J. Lang, and T.-W. Chou, Experimental and theoretical studies of fabric compaction behavior in resin transfer molding, *Materials Science and Engineering*, A317, 2001, pp. 188-196.
- [13] B. Chen and T.-W. Chou, Compaction of woven-fabric preforms: nesting and multi-layer deformation, *Composite Science and Technology*, **60**, 2000, pp. 242-254.
- [14] P. Potluri and T.V. Sagar, Compaction modeling of textile preforms for composite structures, *Composites Structures*, 2008, pp. 177-185.
- [15] J. Hu and A. Newton, Low-load lateral-compression behavior of woven fabrics, *Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1997, pp. 242-254.
- [16] Y. R. Kim, S. P. McCarthy, and J. P. Fanucci, Compressibility and relaxation of fiber reinforcements during composite processing, *Polymer composites*, **12**, 1991, pp. 13-19.
- [17] D. Becker, M. Brzeski, D. Linster, and P. Mitschang, Preform compaction and deformation during through-the-thickness impregnation. *Proceeding of ICCM 19, Montreal, Canada, 2013*.
- [18] G. Rieber, *Einfluss von textilen Parametern auf die Permeabilität von Multifilamentgeweben für Faserkunststoffe*. Dissertation TU Kaiserslautern, 2011.
- [19] G. Rieber and P. Mitschang, 2D Permeability changes due to stitching seams, *Composites Part A – Applied Science and Technology*, **41**, 1, 2010, pp. 2-7.
- [20] A. Hammami and B. R. Gebart, Analysis of the vacuum infusion molding process, *Polymer composites*, **21**, 1, 2000, pp. 28-40.
- [21] X. Liu, P. Falzon, R. Sweeting, and R. Paton, Effective compressibility and permeability of multi-layer non-crimp fiberglass reinforcements, *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites*, **23**, 8, 2004, pp. 861-879.
- [22] R. A. Saunders, C. Lekakou, and M. G. Bader, Compression in the processing of polymer composites 1. A mechanical and microstructural study for different glass fabrics and resins, *Composites Science and Technology*, **59**, 7, 1999, pp. 983-993.
- [23] P. Kelly, R. Umer, and S. Bickerton, Viscoelastic response of dry and wet fibrous materials during infusion processes, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **37**, 6, 2006, pp. 868-873.
- [24] A. A. Somashekar, S. Bickerton, and D. Bhattacharyya, Exploring the non-elastic compression deformation of dry glass fibre reinforcements, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, 2, 2007, pp. 183-200.
- [25] F. Robitaille and R. Gauvin, Compaction of textile reinforcements for composites manufacturing. III: reorganization of the fiber network, *Polymer composites*, **20**, 1, 1999.